

IS LEG NUMBNESS DISSATISFYING FOR PATIENTS AFTER LUMBAR SPINE SURGERY

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the impact of leg numbness on postoperative patient satisfaction following lumbar spine surgery.

Study Design: Prospective observational cohort study.

Place & Duration of Study: This study was conducted at Department of Orthopaedics & Spine Centre, Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital, Lahore from June to September 2024.

Methodology: A cohort of 74 patients who underwent lumbar spine surgery was included. Patient satisfaction was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for low back pain (LBP), leg pain (LP), and leg numbness (LN). Functional outcomes were evaluated using the Japanese Orthopedic Association (JOA) score. Preoperative and postoperative scores were compared to determine improvements in symptoms and overall satisfaction.

Results: Postoperative assessments showed significant improvements in LBP, LP, and LN. Leg numbness scores improved from a preoperative mean of 5.81 ± 2.58 to a postoperative mean of 1.55 ± 1.90 ($p < 0.001$). However, 18% of patients reported dissatisfaction with the surgical outcome, with persistent leg numbness identified as a major cause. A significant correlation was found between preoperative and persistent postoperative leg numbness.

Conclusion: Although lumbar decompression surgery is effective in reducing pain, leg numbness remains a notable factor contributing to postoperative dissatisfaction. Properly addressing patient expectations before surgery and implementing strategies to further reduce leg numbness may enhance overall patient satisfaction and outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Patient satisfaction is increasingly being used as a patient centered measure to assess quality of care and outcomes following spine surgery. Studies looking at relationship between patient's expectations and spine surgery satisfaction have produced conflicting results.^{1,2}

Lumbar spinal stenosis (LSS) is a common condition which causes a number of signs and symptoms such as lower back pain, leg pain and leg numbness. These impair quality of life of patient.^{2,3} Common causes of LSS are: osteophyte formation, ligamentum flavum thickening and hypertrophy of facet joints etc.⁴ If

symptoms don't improve with conservative measures, surgery is done, most often decompression surgery. Preoperative symptoms are usually well improved with decompression surgery and many studies have shown good outcomes.^{5,6,7}

Another common condition with similar signs and symptoms is lumbar disk herniation (LDH). Patients most commonly complaint of lower back pain, discomfort, tingling and numbness in leg. These symptoms impair walking capacity and daily activities of patients. If symptoms don't improve with conservative measures, surgery commonly disc excision is performed. Following surgery patients may experience leg numbness which might reduce patient satisfaction. The numbness increases with walking and standing.^{8,9}

Patient's quality of life is significantly impacted by primary symptoms of LSS and LDH which include claudication, lower extremity pain, discomfort and numbness. These symptoms are usually well improved after surgery except leg numbness, which significantly impairs patient's ability to walk and is a cause of patient dissatisfaction after lumbar spine surgery.^{10,11}

Low patient satisfaction is reported in about 30% of patients after lumbar spine surgery.⁵ A study by Katz et al. showed that 22% of patients are dissatisfied following surgery. Patients have a variety of symptoms and, many of which persist after surgery, making it challenging to determine factors affecting patient satisfaction.¹² Another study showed that more than 25% of patients need subsequent surgery after surgery for LSS and over 30% of patients are dissatisfied after surgery.¹³ The failure to assess numbness may be the cause of patient dissatisfaction despite of positive clinical results.⁶

Lumbar spine surgery succeeds in relieving pain, with residual leg numbness being the most frequent postoperative complication that may influence patient satisfaction. The effects of postoperative pain relief and functional benefits are well-reported, but whether

persistent numbness influences perceived operative success is uncertain.

Methodology

This prospective study aimed to evaluate patients who underwent lumbar spine decompression surgery, including disc excision, at a single medical center. The study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and received approval from the Institutional Review Board at the institution. The analysis included consecutive patients undergoing lumbar spine decompression surgery from June 2024 to September 2024. The inclusion criteria were: (1) significant lumbar spinal stenosis or disc herniation; (2) Radiculopathy with or without lower back pain; (3) failure of conservative management for over 6 weeks; and (4) treatment with lumbar spine posterior decompression surgery or disc excision. Exclusion criteria included: (1) lumbar spine instability; (2) cauda equina syndrome; (3) lumbar spine deformity; (4) history of tumor, trauma, or previous spinal surgery; (5) lumbar spine fusion or fixation surgery; and (6) intraoperative or postoperative complications, such as dural tear or infection.

Data collection involved enrolling patients who met the inclusion criteria and were admitted for surgery during the specified period. After obtaining informed consent, basic demographic and clinical data were gathered, including patient name, age, gender, address, contact number, and diagnosis based on clinical examination and radiographic findings. Low back pain (LBP), leg pain (LP), and leg numbness (LN) were measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS), and the Japanese Orthopedic Association (JOA)¹⁴ score was recorded. Following the planned surgery, during the follow-up visit, LBP, LP, and LN were reassessed using VAS, and the JOA score was updated. Additionally, patient satisfaction was assessed, with responses categorized as very dissatisfied, dissatisfied, neutral, satisfied, or very satisfied.

Criterion	Points
Motor function	
Paralysis	1
Upper extremity	
Fine motor function massively decreased	2
Fine motor function decelerated	3
Discreet weakness in hands or proximal arm	4
Normal function	5
Motor function	
Unable to walk	1
Lower extremity	
Need walking aid on flat floor	2
Need handrail on stairs	3
Able to walk without walking aid, but inadequate	4
Normal function	5
Sensory	
Upper extremity/lower extremity/trunk	
Apparent sensory loss	1
Minimal sensory loss	2
Normal function	3
Bladder function	
Urinary retention	1
Severe dysfunction	2
Mild dysfunction	3
Normal function	4
Total score	0–17

The lower the score the more severe the deficits. Normal function 16 + 17, grade 1: 12–15, grade 2: 8–11, grade 3: 0–7. Weight of the criterion in percentage of 17 points: upper extremity 23.5%; lower extremity 23.5%; sensory 3 × 11.8% (total: 35.4%); bladder and bowel function 17.6%

Figure 1. Japanese Orthopaedic Association (JOA)¹⁴

Results

Table 1 Demographic characteristics of patients

Variables	N (%)	Mean(SD) Range
Gender		
Male	45(60.8)	
Female	29(39.2)	
Age(years)		38.50 (11.26) (19-65)
Follow up period (days)		62.42(28.91) (22-129)

Table 2 Clinical parameters

	Pre-op	Post-op	p-value
Lower back pain	6.91±2.31	1.50±1.56	<.001
Leg pain	7.72±1.31	1.65±1.93	<.001
Leg numbness	5.81±2.58	1.55±1.90	<.001
JOA score	15.15±1.32	16.55±.88	<.001

Table 3 Pearson Correlation Between Postoperative Variables and Patient Satisfaction Level (n = 74)

Variable	r	p-value
Postoperative Lower Back Pain VAS	-0.637	<0.001
Postoperative Leg Pain VAS	-0.752	<0.001
Postoperative Leg Numbness VAS	-0.5	<0.001
Postoperative JOA Score	0.636	<0.001

Figure 2. Distribution of patients according to different procedures done

Figure 3. Satisfaction level of patients after surgical intervention

Of the 74 patients included, 60.8% were male (n=45), and 39.2% were female (n=29), indicating a slight male predominance in the sample. The mean age of the patients was 38.50 years, with a standard deviation of 11.26, suggesting a relatively young to middle-aged

population ranging from 19 to 65 years. The follow-up period after surgery had a mean duration of 62.42 days (SD = 28.91), ranging from 22 to 129 days. (Table 1) The findings from Table 2 indicate a significant improvement in leg numbness following lumbar spine

surgery, with the pre-operative mean score of 5.81 ± 2.58 , reducing to a post-operative mean score of 1.55 ± 1.90 ($p < 0.001$). This reduction suggests that surgical intervention effectively alleviates leg numbness. The most common procedure is "Disc excision L4-L5," with 17 occurrences (23% of the total). "MISS disc excision L4-L5 & L5-S1" (5.4%) and other combinations such as "Disc excision L4-L5 + Laminectomy" (2.7%) indicate the variety of surgical approaches being used. Minimally invasive (MISS) procedures like "MISS disc excision L4-L5" (16.2%) and "MISS disc excision L5-S1" (14.9%) make up a significant portion of the procedures. Several other procedures like "UBE Disc Excision L3-L4 + Decompression L4-L5" and "Posterior Decompression L4-L5" are less common but still contribute to the overall distribution. (Figure 2)

There was a significant negative correlation between patient satisfaction and postoperative lower back pain, leg pain, and leg numbness, indicating that higher levels of pain and numbness were associated with lower satisfaction levels. In contrast, a positive correlation was observed between the postoperative JOA score and satisfaction, suggesting that better functional outcomes were linked to greater patient satisfaction. All correlations were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). (Table 3)

Moreover, the patient satisfaction data (Figure 3) shows that the majority of patients (82%) were either "Satisfied" or "Very Satisfied" post-surgery, indicating that the improvement in symptoms, including leg numbness, contributed positively to overall satisfaction levels.

Discussion

The conversation on leg numbness as a postoperative symptom following lumbar spine surgery is critical to understanding patient satisfaction and overall surgical outcomes. Although clinical parameters such as leg pain and low back pain have improved significantly, residual leg numbness remains an important issue that can adversely affect patient satisfaction. In this context, this phenomenon is best seen in the patients who undergo LSS and lumbar disc herniation, where a significant number of patients perceive dissatisfaction postoperatively, often correlating with residual numbness.¹⁵

Several studies have reported the clinical outcomes of lumbar surgery; however, there are only a few reports on the recovery from LN following lumbar surgery.^{10,14,16, 17} The present study indicates that although decompression surgeries end chronic leg pains, they are not very effective in eliminating leg numbness. For example, Ogura et al.'s study asserted that residual leg numbness was the one of the commonly presenting complaints after decompression surgery and was correlated with a lower satisfaction level. A total of 116 patients were included. All three components had correlation with patient satisfaction with the correlation efficient of 0.30 in LBP, 0.22 in leg pain, and 0.33 in numbness. Numbness had greatest correlation efficient value. The study showed that numbness has a greater impact than leg/back pain on patient satisfaction in patients undergoing decompression for LSS. The study suggests not only LBP and leg pain but also numbness should be evaluated pre- and postoperatively.⁸ Similarly, Yan et al. have reported that the patients who develop numbness of the legs after ambulation expressed decreased satisfaction and that the appearance of numbness significantly affects the perceived success of the surgical procedure.¹¹ It has also been reported that longer durations of preoperative numbness are predictors of postoperative outcome, with a higher rate of residual numbness and lower patient satisfaction.¹⁶

Another study revealed that patient satisfaction had the strongest correlation with the postoperative JOA score. Our findings are consistent with this study as our study also shows a strong correlation between patient satisfaction and postoperative JOA scores.¹⁷ The findings of our study show similarities and differences in patient outcomes and methodologies. The Zou et al. study analyzed a larger sample size of 314 patients, while our study included 74 patients with a slight male predominance (60.8%) and a mean age of 38.50 years ($SD = 11.26$). The follow-up period differed significantly, with the Zou et al. study conducting a comprehensive 12-month follow-up, whereas our study had a shorter mean follow-up duration of 62.42 days ($SD = 28.91$), ranging from 22 to 129 days. Both studies demonstrated significant improvements in leg numbness (VAS-LN) after surgery. In the Zou et al. study, the preoperative VAS-LN mean score of 3.49 ± 2.44 reduced steadily to 1.26

± 0.96 at 12 months, while in our study, the preoperative mean score was higher at 5.81 ± 2.58 , decreasing to 1.55 ± 1.90 ($p < 0.001$) postoperatively.¹⁸

In conclusion, while lumbar spine surgery can lead to significant improvements in symptoms such as leg pain and low back pain, the persistence of leg numbness remains a critical factor influencing patient satisfaction. Future studies should focus on identifying effective strategies to manage and mitigate residual numbness, as well as enhancing preoperative counseling to align patient expectations with potential surgical outcomes. This multifaceted approach could lead to improved satisfaction rates and better overall outcomes for patients undergoing lumbar spine surgery.

Limitation

First, duration of pre-operative symptoms was not recorded. Although some patients were able to give information about exact duration of symptoms but this information was not recorded. Second, no differentiation was done between residual leg numbness and new onset leg numbness after surgery. Third, follow up period in this study is short; studies with longer follow up period are required. Additionally, patient's pre-operative expectations should be studied and their relation to patient satisfaction.

Conclusion

Leg numbness significantly impacts patient satisfaction after lumbar spine surgery. Despite improvements in pain and function, patients with higher postoperative numbness reported greater dissatisfaction. Preoperative counseling and strategies to reduce postoperative numbness are essential to enhance overall satisfaction.

Ethical Approval

The study was approved by The Ethics Committee of Ghurki Trust & Teaching Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

Patient Consent

Informed consent was taken from all patients before their enrollment into the study. Also, all identifiable patient data have been deleted to maintain privacy

Competing Interest

The author declares no competing interests.

Authors Contribution

AUR and AH jointly proposed the study and prepared the final draft. SKK, RA and AUZ contributed in the study design, collected the data and done critical review of final draft. All authors approved the final manuscript.

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Disclosures

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